

Parametric Variations of English and Ikwerre Sentence Structures

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Abstract

This study examined the parametric variations of the sentence structures of English and Ikwerre languages. This is in order to foreground areas of differences and similarities to curb the challenges that come with learning the English language by the speakers of the Ikwerre language. The study adopted Lado's Contrastive Analysis as its theoretical framework and employed the descriptive research design. The data of this study were obtained from the native speakers of Isiokpo dialect of the Ikwerre language. Findings revealed that the English and Ikwerre languages are both non-pro-drop languages and they share the same basic syntactic structures which include the SV, SVA, SVO, SVOO, SVC, SVOC, and SVOA structures. The study further reveals that despite these similarities, there are some parametric variations that differentiate the Ikwerre language from the English language such as the head parameter and wh-parameter. These dissimilarities affect the Ikwerre/English bilinguals' proficiency in speeches and writings. The study, therefore concluded that the knowledge of these parametric variations will enable speakers of the Ikwerre language to surmount any learning challenge engendered by these variations in the course of learning the English language. Thus, the study recommended among others that the teachers of the English language should design the curriculum, prioritising the areas constituting problems as a result of the dissimilarities between the target language and the native languages.

Keywords: Ikwerre, Variations, Sentence Structures, Parametric Variations, Ikwerre Sentence Structure

Introduction

The Ikwerre language is spoken by the Ikwerre people. They constitute one of the major ethnic groups in Rivers State, in the south-south region of Nigeria and occupy four local government areas out of the twenty-four local government areas in the State, which include Port Harcourt, Obio/Akpor, Emohua, and Ikwerre Local Government Areas. The speakers of the Ikwerre language refer to themselves as "Iwhuruonha," meaning proper native (Wotogbe & Lawrence-Hart, 2023) and the language as "Ikwerre." According to Alerechi (2017), the language has twenty-four dialects that are spoken across the four local government areas mentioned above. These dialects are: Rumuekpe, Rundele, Odeegnu, Emohua, Ogbakiri, Akpo, Obio, Aluu, Igwuruta, Omagwa, Isiokpo,

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Ibaa/Obele, Ipo, Ozuaha, Omuanwa, Ubima, Akpabu, Egbeda, Omadeeme, Elele, Omudioga, Ubimini, Omerelu and Apani.

The Ikwerre language is the first language (L1) of many members of the Ikwerre speech community. Just as every language embodies and adheres to peculiar rules and principles that govern them, so does Ikwerre. These rules account for the acceptable patterns by which words of that language are linked to produce larger units, such as phrases and clauses. Although, there are universal rules that cut across all natural languages; there also exist set parameters that distinguishes one language from the other. These parameters are the head parameter, the Wh-parameter, and the Null subject or pro-drop parameters. They are known to be responsible for the syntactic differences in languages.

Languages differ in structure. These differences in structure often times pose problems to the learner as the structures of the first language are sometimes transferred to the target language. This study therefore examines the parametric variations of the English and Ikwerre sentence structures so as to identify areas of differences that may pose difficulty to the Ikwerre learners of English as a second language.

Principles and Parameters of the Universal Grammar

The theory of UG posits that there are common language principles that cut across all human languages and are genetically ingrained in the language faculty of a child to ease the burden of language learning. According to Radford (2009), Chomsky's Universal Grammar (UG) theory explains children's rapid language acquisition by proposing that innate grammatical principles guide how grammar operates in all languages. Since these principles are inborn and not learned, the child's learning burden is reduced, making natural language grammar highly learnable.

On the other hand of UG are the parametric properties that distinguish one language from another. They are regarded as the non-shared attributes of a particular language. Ndimele (2004) notes that parametrised variations are triggered by certain features of the UG that are unavailable to certain linguistic groups. This is further asserted that the grammatical differences among languages are characterised in terms of a limited set of parameters. There are three major parameters along which languages differ in terms of grammatical structure, they are: the Head Parameter, Wh-parameter, and Null subject or Pro-drop Parameters. Each of these parameters involves a binary choice from which a language chooses only one value, either positive or negative, for each of the parameters.

- 1. The Head Parameter:** This is a word order parameter. In syntax, it is compulsory for every phrase to have a head. The head of the phrase that determines the syntactic category of the phrase. For example, the noun phrase "the hungry old-looking man" has its head as "man" while "hungry and old-looking" are the complements of the head. The principle of headedness holds that, every grammatical structure is a projection of the head, and that the placement of the head element, is responsible for

syntactic differences among languages. The head and its complements are tied together in a close relationship in phrases. This is evident in phrases such as the Noun Phrase (NP), Verb Phrase (VP), Prepositional Phrase (PP), and others. The head parameter makes it possible for some languages to be either head-initial and complement final or head-final and complement-initial, showing different structural arrangements of the constituents. Cook (1988) cited in Richard (2023) stated that “in English, all heads (whether nouns, verbs, prepositions or adjectives, etc.) normally precede their complements.

2. **The Wh-Parameter:** This parameter regulates the option of preposing a wh-constituent or leaving it in place (“in situ”) in wh-questions (Huang & Ian, 2016). In simpler terms, Ndimele (2004) explains that:

the Wh-parameter is concerned with the position of a Wh-word in overt syntax. It makes a distinction between languages where a question-word must obligatorily move to the leftmost edge of the sentence in overt syntax and those where the question-word can remain in-situ (i.e. in bases-generated position) without showing any evidence of overt syntactic movement (p.6).

Ndimele (2004) further notes that the Wh-parameter involves a binary choice so that languages are distinguished in terms of those that can allow obligatory syntactic wh-movement and those that cannot. In the English language, Wh-constituents appear in sentence-initial position except in echoic questions, this is because the language shows overt syntactic movement.

3. **The Null Subject or Pro-drop Parameters:** The basic observation motivating the Null subject or pro-drop parameter postulates that some languages allow a definite pronominal subject of a finite clause to remain unexpressed. In contrast, other languages require it to be expressed as a nominal bearing the subject function. Traditional grammars of languages such as Latin and Greek relate this to the fact that personal endings on the verb distinguish the person and the number of the subject, thereby making a subject pronoun redundant (Huang and Ian, 2016).

Ndimele (2004) notes that the Null subject parameter, just like the Wh-parameter, involves a binary choice. This is to allow a language to choose any of the binary values of the parameter. Languages that allow a definite pronominal subject of a finite clause to remain unexpressed are referred to as null subject or pro-drop languages, while those that do not allow such are called non-pro-drop languages. The English language is an example of a non-pro-drop language whereas, languages like Spanish and Italian are pro-drop languages.

Theoretical Framework

Contrastive Analysis (henceforth, CA) is a theory introduced by Robert Lado in 1957 in his *Linguistics Across Culture*. It is employed when making a side-by-side comparison of

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the features of two or more languages that belong to different families of languages, usually a target language and a source language. CA upholds the idea that no two languages are the same, and as such, analyses two or more languages by bringing to bear their differences and similarities. Robert Lado believes that pointing out the differences and similarities of the languages will make the learning of the target language easier for the learner. According to Gast (2016, cited in Udemmadu & Chinyeaka 2017), “contrastive studies mostly deal with the comparison of languages that are ‘socio-culturally linked.’” Udemmadu & Chinyeaka (2017) explain that CA compares “languages whose speech communities overlap in some way, typically through (natural or instructed) bilingualism,” in this case, the English and Ikwerre languages, so as to identify their structural differences and similarities.

The theory, according to Nwizug (2022), reveals the point of departure as well as the meeting point of two languages basically for pedagogical reasons. Lado (1957, cited in Nwizug 2022) highlights that the points of departure in a native and a target language (L2) are likely going to pose a linguistic challenge to the L2 learner, while the similarities in both languages may be harmless. This implies that CA is useful in ascertaining certain aspects of the target language that pose serious challenges to the learner compared to other aspects. In other words, the theory is useful in predicting the language problems of learners and as well aids in the development of teaching materials for L2 learners to foster seamless teaching and learning of the target language.

Sentence Structures of the English and Ikwerre Languages

The structural arrangement of a sentence differs from language to language. In the English language, the syntactic arrangement of constituents takes the SVO (Subject, Verb, Object) structure. It is also noted that there are about seven basic sentence structures of the English Language which include: the SV, SVA, SVC, SVO, SVOO, SVOA and SVOC sentence structures. This implies that the sentence structure of the English language comprises the subject, verb, object, complement and adjunct (SVOCA).

Just as the English language, the sentence in Ikwerre is composed of the SVOCA which also bears within it the primary sentence structure of the language –the SVO. Moreso, the seven basic sentence structures captured in the English language are also found in Ikwerre. The examples below will be focused on the sentence structure of Ikwerre language since that of the English language is already known.

a) SV: subject + intransitive verb

1. Joseph na gba'so.
 Subj. Aux.V Lex.V
 (Joseph is running.)
2. O biaru.
 Subj. Lex.V
 (He came.)

Sentence 1 and 2 are examples of simple sentences that are composed of just the subject (which is usually a noun or pronoun) and a verb. As exemplified above, the Ikwerre language can make short simple sentences with the SV structure.

b) SVA: subject + verb + adverbial complement

3. Nda m wu nu Lagos.
Subj. Poss. V Pre. O
(Father-my live in Lagos)
My father lives in Lagos

Noun phrases in the Ikwerre language are head initial and complement final, this is exemplified in the example above where the possessive pronoun “m” translated as “my” which functions as a determiner and complement to the noun “nda” translated as “father” is positioned after the noun.

4. Elu zoru n’ ahia
Subj. Vpst Prep O
(Rain fell in market.)
Rain fell in the market.

The literal translation of the sentence, “Elu zoru na’hia” is “The sky rained in the market” but in context and for the need of clarity and relatability to the English language, it is better translated as “Rain fell in the market.” It is worth noting that in the Ikwerre language, the functional categories like the definite and indefinite articles which are apparent in the English language are not prominent in the Ikwerre language. An example is the sentence above; in the English translation “Rain fell in the market.”, the definite article “the” is obvious and indispensable whereas in the Ikwerre translation, the article is not represented.

Sentences 3 and 4 are examples of the SVA structure. Sentences with the SVA structure consist of the Subject, verb, and adverbial complement. The adverbial complements provide essential information about the verb in a sentence, for example, the adverbial complement of sentence 3 is “in Lagos/nu Lagos” which gives information about the verb “lives/whu” thereby answering the question of where my father lives. Sometimes, the adverbial complement is introduced with a preposition as is the case in the examples above. This implies that in cases like that, the prepositional phrase (PP) functions as the adverbial complement of the sentence. , The Ikwerre translation of sentence 3 exemplifies the fact that the noun phrase in the Ikwerre language is head initial and complement final, this is seen above where the possessive pronoun “m” translated as “my” which functions as a determiner and complement to the noun “nda” translated as “father” is positioned after the noun.

c) SVC: subject + linking verb + subject complement

5. I ma rumma
Spro V Comp.
(You are beautiful.)
6. Chizi bu ye te’ri.

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Subj V O
(Chizi is a person who dances (dancer).)
Chizi is a dancer.

Sentences 5 and 6 are examples of the SVC structure. The unique component of the structure is the subject complement. A **subject complement** usually follows a **linking verb** and provides more information about the subject of the sentence. Subject complements can take the form of **predicative nominatives** as seen in sentence 6 “ye te’ri” translated as “a dancer” or **predicative adjectives** as in sentence 5 “marumma” translated as “beautiful.

d) SVO: subject + transitive verb + direct object

7. Chimenum zi n’ oro.
Subj Vpres prep. O
(Chimenum is at home.)

8. Azunda reru ogbo-ali nda a.
Subj Vpst O poss.
(Azunda sold car father my)
Azunda sold his father’s car.

Sentences 7-8 are examples of the SVO structure. In sentence 8, the subject is the noun “Chimenum,” the verb is “is/zi” while the object of the sentence is the PP which consists of the preposition “at/nu” and the noun “home/oro.” In the Ikwerre translation of sentence 8, the subject is the proper noun “Azunda,” the verb “reru” translated as “sold” and the object of the sentence is the noun phrase “ogbo-ali nda a” literally translated as “land boat (car) father his”. The objective part of the sentence reveals that in Ikwerre, the modified precedes the modifier, as seen in the NP “nda a” translated as “father his”. The modified, being the noun “nda” which means “father” is placed before the modifier which is the personal pronoun “a” transliterated as “his”. This interprets the notion that the noun phrases in Ikwerre is head initial and complement final unlike it is in English.

e) SVOO: subject + transitive verb + indirect object + direct object

9. Azunda kpasiri nda a obu-owhe-ahu.
Subj Vpst iO Poss dO
(Azunda provoked father his anger)
Azunda provoked his father to anger.

10. Daniel zunu wene a ogbo-ali ikne.
Subj Vpst iO Poss. dO
(Daniel bought brother his land boat (car) new)
Daniel bought his brother a new car.

Sentences 9-10 show the SVOO structure. This sentence structure uniquely carries two objects; an indirect and a direct object which take the form of predicative normative (nouns or pronouns).

f) SVOA: subject + transitive verb + direct object + adverbial complement

11. Ai riri arusi n' abali echile.
Subj Vpst O Prep O Adv.
(We ate rice in night yesterday)
We ate rice last night.
12. O wuru oro nu ohaezi.
Subj Vpst O Prep Adv.
(He built house in city)
He built a house in the city.

Sentences 11-12 are examples of the SVOA sentence structure of the English language. The structure comprises the subject, verb, direct object, and adverbial complement. For example, in sentence 12; the subject is the pronoun "He/O", the verb "built/wuru", the direct object is the NP "a house/oro" and the adverbial complement is the PP "in the city/ni ohaezi" which gives information on where he built the house.

g) SVOC: subject + transitive verb + direct object + object complement

13. O mer' a obu-oso.
Subj Vpst Opro Comp.
(She made him happy)
She made him happy.
14. Be gwuru-ahua nwo be, Ikenga.
Subj Vpst O Poss. Comp.
(They named child their, Ikenga)
They named their child, Ikenga.

Sentences 13 and 14 are examples of the SVOC sentence structure which consists of the subject, verb, object and the object complement.

The Structural Parametric Variations In English And Ikwerre Languages

1. The Head Parameter: The principle of headedness holds that every grammatical structure is a projection of the head. The head and its complements are tied together in a close relationship in phrases. This is evident in phrases such as the noun, verb, prepositional phrases, etc. The head parameter makes it possible for some languages to be either head-initial and complement final or head-final and complement-initial, showing different structural arrangements of the constituents. The English language has head-final and complement-initial, whereas the Ikwerre language has head-initial and complement-final.

i. English and Ikwerre Noun Phrases: A noun phrase is made up of a noun head and its complements such as the determiners and the pre- or postmodifiers. Ndimele describes a determiner as a word which signals the presence of a noun.

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Determiner is a cover word for articles, demonstratives, possessives, quantifiers, numerals and interrogatives. In syntagmatic relationship, English grammar allows all determiners to precede the noun they reference. Hence, in the grammar of headedness, the English noun phrase is complement initial and head final whereas the position of the constituents of a noun phrase in the Ikwerre language is different from that of the English language. In Ikwerre, the noun is placed first, followed by its complements. This implies that in syntagmatic relationships, Ikwerre syntax allows all determiners and complements of the noun to post-modify the noun they reference. Therefore, the researcher notes that the Ikwerre language is head initial and complement final. for example:

15. Amgba kuwaruokuwa
Modified modifier
(plate broken)
The broken plate.

16. Yewere marumma
Modified modifier
(woman beautiful)
The beautiful woman

The Ikwerre translation of examples 15 to 16 indicate that in noun phrases in Ikwerre language, the modified comes before the modifier. When an adjective is used to modify a noun in a phrase, the adjective is placed after the noun. An example is the Noun Phrase, “Yewere marumma”, which is translated “woman beautiful”. It shows that the head of the phrase, “yewere”, comes before the complement, “marumma”, thereby affirming that the Ikwerre language is head initial and complement final.

Also, it is observed that categories such as definite and indefinite articles which are apparent in the English language are not prominent in the Ikwerre language. In the examples above, the articles in the English sentences are omitted in their Ikwerre equivalent. For example, in the phrase, “The broken plate”, the definite article, “the,” is apparent, unlike its Ikwerre equivalent of the sentence, “amgba kuwaruokuwa”, which is literally translated as “plate broken”. It is seen that the definite article, “the”, is rather implied rather than being expressly written like it is in the English language. Another example is the NP below:

17. Omu-okwukwo ne whe-ahu.
Modified modifier
(Students are angry)
Some students.

The English equivalent of the example above is, “some angry students”, but the Ikwerre translation displaces the quantifier, “some”. This is because in some cases, in Ikwerre language, determiners are subsumed into the head word or completely omitted in noun phrases.

ii. **The Structure or Arrangement of Personal Pronouns in Noun Phrases:** In the syntax of the English language, the structure or arrangement of personal pronouns begins with the third person followed by the second person, and then the first person, as in, “Azunda, you and I are friends” whereas in Ikwerre language, the sequence is from the first person followed by the second person, and lastly the third person. For instance, “me nu ge nu Azunda bu enyi”, is translated as (I (first person) and (conjunction) you(second person) and (conjunction) Azunda (third person) are friends; meaning: “I, you and Azunda are friends.” Hence, it is convenient for an Ikwerre learner of the English language to use the direct translation of “me nu ge nu Azunda bu enyi” which is “I, you and Azunda are friends” instead of the correct form “Azunda, you and I are friends”.

2. **Wh-parameter:** This parameter regulates the option of preposing a wh-constituent or leaving it in place (“in situ”) in wh-questions (Huang & Ian 2016), the English language requires the movement of the wh-constituent from its in-situ position to the SpecCP position except in echo questions but in Ikwerre, the reverse is the case, in that, the wh-constituent remains at the in situ and is therefore presented as an echo question, for example:

18. I bu ye?
(You are who?)
Who are you?
19. Nwo i zi nu hele?
(Your child is in where?)
Where is your child?

The examples above show that the Ikwerre language hosts the wh-constituents at the sentence-final position. Consequently, an Ikwerre learner of the English language finds it convenient to use an echo question even where unnecessary because it aligns with the syntax of his native language. However, this is not applicable in all cases as sometimes, the Ikwerre language hosts the wh-constituent at the sentence-initial position like the English language, for example:

20. Kini bu ahwnua i?
(what is name your?)
What is your name?
21. Nyehele bu nda i?
(Who is father your?)
Who is your father?

The examples above show rare cases where the Ikwerre language hosts the wh-constituent at the sentence-initial position like the English language except that, the possessive pronoun “your” is placed at the sentence-final position instead of at the medial position like the English counterpart.

In conclusion, the two major parameters that differentiates syntactic structure of the Ikwerre language from that of the English language are the head and wh parameters.

The Shared Linguistic Parameters in the Sentence Formation of Both Languages

1. The Null Subject or Pro-drop Parameters: The Ikwerre language shares only one linguistic parameter with the English Language which is that both languages are non-pro-drop languages. This implies that the English and Ikwerre languages require the expression of the definite pronominal subject of a finite clause, that is, both languages require definite pronominals to be expressed as a nominal bearing the subject function in clause or sentence. For example:

Susan is my best friend.

Using a pronominal subject to replace the subject/noun “Susan”, the English language will say:

22. She is my best friend.

While the Ikwerre language will say:

O bu eyi oma m.

(She is friend good my)

She is my good friend.

Other examples include:

23. English: They have agreed.

Ikwerre: Be kweri-lem.

(They agreed-have)

24. English: He is my father-in-law.

Ikwerre: O bun nda nzi m.

(he is father husband my)

He is my husband’s father.

The examples above show that Ikwerre is a non-pro-drop language just as the English language, that is, they require the expression of their pronominal subjects in sentences. The Ikwerre language uses the personal pronoun “O” to represent the masculine, feminine and neuter gender, in other words, “O” is translated as “he/she/it”. Example 47 shows that Ikwerre does not have a single unit of word for “father-in-law”, therefore, the word “my father-in-law” is translated as “nda nzi’m” which means “my husband’s father”.

Conclusion

This work establishes the parametric variations between the English and Ikwerre languages. It reveals that although both languages are non-pro-drop languages, that is, they require the expression of their definite pronominals as subject in clauses and sentences, both languages also share the same basic sentence structure of the SVO. Also, there are parameters that distinguish English from Ikwerre such as the head and wh-parameters. The researcher believes that the knowledge of these parametric variations will enable speakers of the Ikwerre language to surmount any learning challenges engendered by these variations in the course of learning the English language. The researcher, therefore, recommends that these parametric variations be put into consideration in curriculum planning of the English language subjects to make easy the teaching and learning of the language.

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